

TRANSFERABLE DEEP LEARNING ARCHITECTURE FOR SIMULTANEOUS PREDICTION OF SURFACE QUALITY AND DIMENSIONAL ACCURACY ACROSS MULTIPLE CNC MACHINING CENTERS

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ABSTRACT:

This research arises from the need identified during the COVID-19 pandemic, where supply chain disruptions highlighted the importance of developing more adaptable manufacturing systems capable of redirecting production between different sites while maintaining quality standards. For this purpose, the application of artificial intelligence has become an imperative necessity.

This work presents the development of a transferable Deep Learning model for simultaneous prediction of surface roughness (Ra) and diameter deviation (Ddev) through process-measured signals (vibrations, forces, acoustic emission, among others) in CNC machining processes, applied across four different manufacturing sites (MS1-MS4) to implement a resilient distributed manufacturing strategy.

CNC turning, surface roughness prediction, diameter deviation prediction, variable cutting parameters, distributed manufacturing, deep learning.

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1. - INTRODUCTION

The European manufacturing industry represents a fundamental pillar of the economy, generating between 20-25% of GDP and 20% of total employment [1]. However, recent crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic have exposed critical vulnerabilities in this sector. During lockdown measures, there was unprecedented disruption of supply chains, forcing manufacturers to rapidly reconvert and reorient production towards new products and processes. This experience evidenced the urgent need to transform the European industry towards a more resilient system, capable of adapting to internal and external disturbances by modifying its mode of operation without losing its operational capacity.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is positioned as a strategic technology to respond to these challenges. Its integration into production environments allows for digital modeling of production lines, optimization of process routes, anticipation of bottlenecks and possible risks in supply chains, facilitating agile responses that ensure continuity, while simultaneously maintaining product quality, sustainability standards, and delivery times.

In this context of vulnerability, machining processes constitute a significant part of manufacturing operations, where prediction and quality control have become critical factors to maintain competitiveness and sustainability. Traditionally, quality control has been carried out through post-manufacturing inspection, resulting in late detection of defects and consequent waste of material and energy. This reactive approach has proven insufficient in the face of current demands for agile and sustainable manufacturing, especially in the context of Industry 4.0.

In this work, AI is not only applied as a method to predict output quality in the CNC machining process at a production center through process-measured signals (vibrations, forces, acoustic emission, among others), but the process is also modeled in different machines corresponding to various production centers. This modeling in different scenarios is essential to address supply chain disruptions by being able to transfer production from one center to another while maintaining the required quality standards. This work focuses on the prediction of critical parameters in machining such as surface roughness (Ra) and diameter deviation (Ddev).

	Arquitectura de Deep Learning transferible para la Predicción Simultánea de Calidad Superficial y Precisión Dimensional para diferentes centros de mecanizado CNC	COMPUTER SCIENCE 1203.04 Artificial Intelligence
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Many works have been published analyzing how to predict surface roughness in machining processes using AI techniques on high-frequency time signals. In some cases, machine learning (ML) techniques are used, requiring preprocessing of signals to extract relevant features in both the time and frequency domains. In [2], this feature extraction is performed on force signals in the time and frequency domains in a robot-assisted polishing process, demonstrating that both domains provide valuable data for estimating surface roughness. In [3], classical machine learning methods such as decision trees (DT), random forest (RF), support vector machines (SVM), artificial neural networks (ANN), are evaluated for roughness prediction in diamond turning of germanium and copper, finding that both approaches significantly outperform traditional analytical models. In [4], ANN, linear regression, DT, and RF are compared for roughness prediction in Al6061, where neural networks showed the best performance with feed rate and depth of cut data. In [5], RF and Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) models are implemented for continuous monitoring of surface roughness using cutting forces, temperature, and vibration, achieving RMSE less than 0.4 μ m with GPR. In [6], a three-layer ANN is proposed that integrates features extracted from the signal in the time and frequency domains of vibration, force, and current data in real time, achieving a mean absolute percentage error of 1.01% in surface roughness prediction in milling.

On the other hand, deep learning (DL) algorithms avoid this manual feature extraction step, as the algorithm itself performs this task directly when there is a large number of samples [7]. In [8], a physics-informed deep learning (PIDL) model is developed that combines a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a gated recurrent unit (GRU) network with embedded physical knowledge and a physically guided loss function, reducing the mean absolute percentage error by 3.029% compared to existing methods. In [9], three neural network architectures (DNN, CNN, and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)) are evaluated using cutting force signals preprocessed with Fourier transform to predict surface roughness in milling of SUS304 stainless steel, where CNN showed the best analytical efficiency. The training data were obtained through a full factorial design. [10] proposes a SAE-LSTM (Stacked autoencoder – Long Short-Term Memory) architecture with transfer learning for online roughness prediction considering tool wear under variable cutting parameters, achieving a minimum RMSE of 0.027 μ m and MAPE of 1.56. In [11], ML applications in CNC machines are reviewed, including surface quality prediction using neural networks, decision trees, and random forest, highlighting the use of deep learning algorithms for real-time roughness monitoring.

The problem of addressing the prediction of dimensional deviations is much less addressed in the literature. In [12], the prediction of both quality parameters is addressed, but each with a neural network model dedicated to each variable. Special mention is required for [13] as it proposes a methodology based on one-dimensional convolutional neural networks for real-time quality prediction of parts during CNC turning, using raw vibration signals, speeds, and motor torques without manual feature extraction. The developed multi-output model achieves F1 scores above 0.97 for simultaneous classification of surface roughness (Ra, Rz) and dimensional deviation, demonstrating the ability to distinguish between cutting and non-cutting phases with limited training data. The data used in this article are the same as those used in one of the manufacturing sites (MS) of this work, but only with exploratory experiments without testing the models with different parts.

2. - MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1. EXPERIMENTAL CONFIGURATION

For this work, four different manufacturing sites (MS1, MS2, MS3, MS4) were selected, with the objective of demonstrating the feasibility of redirecting production from one site to another quickly to implement distributed manufacturing. For this, it is necessary to generate a digital model based on data from the machining system of each center, which will allow predicting the output quality of the parts in their two most critical parameters: surface roughness and dimensional accuracy throughout the CNC machining process.

Each center has different machining machines of varying ages, which means that the extractable information from each machine is not exactly the same, nor are the process sensorization and sensor locations. This defines 4 different scenarios due to the variability in the signals used to build the four AI-based models. Since it is known that tool wear significantly affects the output surface roughness [10], all experiments were carried out with unworn Sandvik CoromantTM CNMG 12 04 08-MR 4305 tools. The material of the parts used (CK45 steel) is also the same.

Table 1 shows the machines used and the signals obtained in each MS, using sensors from different manufacturers. Although a sampling frequency of 10 kHz would have been more convenient to obtain high-frequency signal features, the limitation to 1 kHz present in two of the MS forced all signals to be resampled to 1 kHz to maintain data consistency. In MS3, in addition to vibration signals in the three axes, an acoustic emission (AE) signal was acquired, whose processing included the root mean square (RMS) value of the amplitude signal captured by the sensors.

Machine	Signals	Number of signals	Sampling rate
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MS1	OKUMA LB10ii turning center with OSP700L controller	vibration: Z, X speed: Z, X, Spindle torque: Z, X, Spindle	8	1 kHz
MS2	DMG Mori NZX 1500	force: Z, X, Y vibration: Z, X, Y	6	10 kHz resampled to 1kHz
MS3	DMG Mori NTX2000/1500S	vibration: Z, X, Y AE RMS	4	10 kHz resampled to 1 kHz
MS4	DMG Gildemeister CTX gamma	vibration: Z, X, Y	3	1 kHz

Table 1. Machines, signals obtained, and sampling frequency for MS1 – MS4.

2.2. EXPERIMENTS AND DATASETS OBTAINED

Two different types of experiments were carried out in each of the MS with the aim of generating data to train and validate the DL model. Since the parts and machine configurations are the same, only the methodology corresponding to MS1 is explained. The objective is to demonstrate that it is possible to infer output quality without directly measuring the parameters of surface roughness (Ra) and diameter deviation (Ddev). However, since it is supervised learning, in each machining phase it is necessary to stop the process and perform intermediate measurements of Ra and Ddev to associate them with the signals captured by the sensors.

Figure 1. (a) Process scheme for Experiment 1 (b) Process scheme for Experiment 2

MS1. Experiment 1 – Dataset 1: Data generation for model training

The experimental approach consisted of performing longitudinal passes (Fig. 1.a) on two cylindrical parts, using various combinations of process parameters through a design of experiments based on Taguchi's L16 orthogonal array [14] in which the parameters of depth of cut (a_p), feed (f_z), and cutting speed (v_c) were varied at four levels. Table 2 shows the variation of these parameters across the 16 combinations evaluated (8 per part). Surface roughness in each pass was measured three times each in sections L1, L2, and L3, resulting in a total of 48 measurements (16×3). As in each pass, the resulting diameter decreased, Ddev was calculated as the resulting diameter minus the nominal diameter, which could take positive and negative values.

The sensors and the machine generated eight signals (spindle torque, spindle speed, vibration in X, vibration in Z, torque in X, torque in Z, speed in X, speed in Z) sampled at 1 kHz to which the measured values of Ra and Ddev were assigned. The duration of each signal during these periods ranged from approximately 0.5 to 2 seconds per pass. A window size of 0.5 seconds was selected to segment the signal in each measurement, with an 80% overlap (window step of 0.1 seconds). This process generated approximately 100 windows per signal.

Cutting speed (v_c) [m/min]	Feed rate (f_z) [mm/rev]	Depth of cut (a_p) [mm]
160, 190, 220, 250	0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5	0.5, 1, 1.5, 2

Table 2. Process parameters of dataset 1

As a special case, MS2 repeated this experiment 1 three times due to obtaining some inconsistent quality parameter. This higher number of samples can be seen in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

MS1. Experiment 2 – Dataset 2: Real parts

Another set of experiments (Fig.2.b) was carried out to manufacture five parts with the design presented in Fig. 2. Table 3 presents the process parameters used during this procedure, which were repeated for the manufacture of the five parts. It should be noted that neither the values of v_c nor the values of f_z are included in experiment 1. The measured signals were identical to those of dataset 1. Signal preprocessing included a windowing of 0.5 seconds without overlapping to segment the signal during these periods. This process generated a total of 163 windows during roughing and 121 windows during finishing throughout the dataset. For each of these sections of the part per pass, measurements of Ra and Ddev were made and assigned to each resulting window.

Fig.2. (a) Drawing and (b) part nabyfactured in experiment 2

Process	Cutting speed (v_c) [m/min]	Feed rate (f_z) [mm/rev]	Depth of cut (a_p) [mm]
Roughing	180	0.30	Varies (defined by CAM)
Finishing	180	0.08	0.5

Table 3. Process parameters for dataset 2

This process was repeated in manufacturing sites MS2, MS3, and MS4, adapting to the available sensors and, consequently, to the signals that can be obtained in each center.

The representation of the quality data obtained shows some variability between the different MS, being much greater for the Ddev values.

Figure 3. Ra for each MS in Experiment 1 and Experiment 2

Figure 4. Ddev for each MS in Experiment 1 and Experiment 2

2.3. DEEP LEARNING MODEL ARCHITECTURE

In this work, DL techniques have been used to model machining processes. DL is characterized by the use of artificial neural network models with multiple layers and differs from classical ML models in that, when trained with large amounts of data, it does not require prior processing to extract relevant features. These DL algorithms are capable of extracting relevant information from the signals without the need for preprocessing.

The developed DL modeling is based on a Wide Deep Convolutional Network (WDCNN) [15] with important modifications by converting the CNN into a separable convolution (Depthwise-Pointwise type separable convolution) [16]. The advantage of this architecture is that the raw signals are simultaneously introduced to the model as a one-dimensional input (1-D input). In the first convolutional layer, larger dimension kernels are used to extract relevant features from the signal and suppress high-frequency noise.

With respect to the original WDCNN algorithm, a separable convolution is used. This technique consists of employing as many filters as input channels independently (component called depthwise) and then linearly combining the result of these in a higher number of filters (component called pointwise). This separable convolution is followed by batch normalization, which ensures that each feature map has a unique mean and standard deviation. This normalization allows for faster convergence during network training and helps reduce overfitting.

Finally, the MaxPooling layer constitutes a subsampling stage to reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps. This configuration implements a progressive hierarchical filtering, where the kernel size decreases exponentially ($128 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 8$), allowing the capture of multi-resolution features from global patterns to fine local details. The consistency in the number of pointwise filters (64) keeps the feature dimensionality constant throughout the network, facilitating the flow of gradients during training.

To this architecture, a conventional dense network with four layers of (100, 50, 50, 50) neurons is added to produce an output of two independent variables. The first two layers show full connection between the neurons, while the last two are interconnected 2 by 2 to particularize the output for the two independent output variables. The activation functions in hidden layers are ReLU, while the output activation function for each output variable is Softmax, which provides membership probabilities for each class that sum to 1.

Fig. 5. Deep Learning Architecture applied. Input: Cn 1 kHz signals x number of available signals. Output N1 and N2 classes: Ra and Ddev.

The classification ranges have been established from UNE-EN ISO 1302:2002 and ISO 286-1:2010 standards for surface roughness and diameter deviation (tolerances), respectively. For this work, which uses supervised learning, the classification ranges used are shown in Table 4 and Table 5. Not all classes established by the ISO standard are covered, but only those that appear in the experiments carried out. In the case of diameter deviation, the IT7 and IT8 classes are grouped into IT9 and the IT10 and IT11 classes into IT13

Class	N6	N7	N8	N9
Roughness Ra (μm)	[0,4 - 0,8)	[0.8 - 1,6)	[1,6 - 3,2)	[3.2 - 6.3)

Table 4. Classes for roughness (Ra) in μm .

Class	IT6	IT9 (includes IT7 and IT8)	IT13 (includes IT10 and IT11)
Negative values	[-0.013, 0)	[-0.052, -0.013)	[-0.330, -0.052)
Positive values	[0,0.013)	[0.013, 0.052)	[0.052, 0.330)

Table 5. Classes for Ddev in mm. The classes, centered at 0, are subdivided according to whether Ddev is positive or negative

As a special consideration, each of the signals also includes moments when the machine is not machining but positioning the tool and the part. Thus, in both cases, a new class called NC (no cutting) has been created for the moments when it is not cutting.

Thus, for each of the MS, the model architecture is particularized according to the available input signals and the model is retrained. Initially, training and validation were performed only with the data from experiment 1, and later validated with the data from experiment 2. However, a domain adaptation problem was identified, which represents a change in the operating and environmental conditions of the machine. This phenomenon is common in industrial environments, as machines do not always operate under their design conditions. In our case, the source domain is defined as the conditions under which the experimental design is executed to train models, and the target domain as the machine conditions for machining real parts.

For this reason, training was carried out with all the data from experiment 1 plus the data from one of the parts from experiment 2. In this way, the operating conditions of part machining are incorporated into the training and the distributions of the features extracted by the DL algorithm are unified. Of the total of these data, 90% was used for training and 10% for validation. The data from the remaining 4 real parts are used for testing.

Table 6 shows large differences in the number of samples between the different MS. This is because signals corresponding to NC states have been included in the dataset. These non-cutting periods are considerably more numerous than the cutting ones.

		Training	%	Validation	%	Test	%
MS1	Total	(1619, 500, 8)	100,00%	(180, 500, 8)	100,00%	(492, 500, 8)	100,00%
MS1	Cutting	(649, 500, 8)	40,08%	(70, 500, 8)	38,89%	(227, 500, 8)	46,14%
MS1	No Cutting	(945, 500, 8)	59,92%	(110, 500, 8)	61,11%	(265, 500, 8)	53,86%

MS2	Total	(7496, 500, 6)	100,00%	(833, 500, 6)	100,00%	(632, 500, 6)	100,00%
MS2	Cutting	(1869, 500, 6)	24,93%	(211, 500, 6)	25,33%	(116, 500, 6)	18,35%
MS2	No Cutting	(5627, 500, 6)	75,07%	(622, 500, 6)	74,67%	(516, 500, 6)	81,65%
MS3	Total	(5245, 500, 4)	100,00%	(583, 500, 4)	100,00%	(963, 500, 4)	100,00%
MS3	Cutting	(1377, 500, 4)	26,25%	(108, 500, 4)	30,87%	(266, 500, 4)	27,62%
MS3	No Cutting	(3868, 500, 4)	73,75%	(403, 500, 4)	69,13%	(697, 500, 4)	72,38%
MS4	Total	(6273, 500, 3)	100,00%	(698, 500, 3)	100,00%	(671, 500, 3)	100,00%
MS4	Cutting	(1417, 500, 3)	22,59%	(150, 500, 3)	21,49%	(238, 500, 3)	35,47%
MS4	No Cutting	(4865, 500, 3)	77,41%	(548, 500, 3)	78,51%	(433, 500, 3)	62,53%

Table 6. Training, validation, and test samples from MS1 to MS4. The three-dimensional matrix means number of samples, number of points in the time sequence, and number of input variables or channels.

This class imbalance requires measures to prevent the model training from focusing only on NC classification, which would provide apparently good but biased training metrics. Therefore, the loss function used in the previous network architecture employs a variant of sparse categorical cross-entropy, called weighted sparse categorical cross-entropy, which allows assigning different weights to each class during loss calculation [17]. This is especially useful in scenarios with class imbalance, where some classes have many more samples than others, allowing higher weights to be assigned to minority classes to balance their influence during training.

Finally, it is necessary to optimize the main hyperparameters of the network, which include the sizes of the convolutional filters, the kernel dimensions, the configuration of the dense layers, the batch sizes, and the learning rates. To identify the most suitable combination of these parameters, a grid search strategy is implemented, due to its thoroughness in systematically exploring configurations. The optimization focuses specifically on the MS3 machining center, as it is the facility that presents the greatest difficulties in achieving good results.

The neural network shown in Fig. 5 already corresponds to the optimized architecture.

The metrics used to validate the model are the confusion matrix and the F1 metric [18]. The first is a fundamental tool for evaluating the performance of classification models. It is a table that compares the model's predictions with the actual values of the dataset, showing how many instances were correctly and incorrectly classified.

The F1 metric is based on the values obtained in the confusion matrix and is calculated using the following formula:

$$F1 = \frac{(2 \times Precision \times Recall)}{Precision + Recall} \quad (1)$$

Where

Precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ (2): Probability that, if the system classifies the roughness/diameter deviation in a certain category, it really belongs to that category.

Recall = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ (3): Measures how many positive values are correctly classified out of the total values that are actually positive

And

TP (True Positive): when the model correctly predicts a positive instance

FP (False Positive): when the model incorrectly predicts a negative instance as positive

FN (False Negative): when the model fails to identify a positive instance, classifying it incorrectly as negative

TN (True Negative): when the model correctly predicts a negative instance

The TP and TN values represent correct classifications, while FP and FN indicate model classification errors.

However, these formulas are traditionally applied in binary classification problems. In multiclass classification, a global F1-score is not calculated directly. Instead, the One-vs-Rest (OvR) approach is used, where the F1-score is calculated for each class separately, treating each class as if it were a binary classification problem. Subsequently, these individual values are averaged to obtain global metrics such as the macro F1-score (unweighted average) or the weighted F1-score (considering the frequency of each class).

All algorithms have been implemented using Python as the programming language, the TensorFlow library for DL model implementation, and accelerated processing techniques using GPU.

3. - RESULTS

Below are the results obtained with the selected metric in training, validation, and test for each of the output variables.

	F1-Score in training					F1-Score in Validation					F1-Score in Test				
	N6	N7	N8	N9	NC	N6	N7	N8	N9	NC	N6	N7	N8	N9	NC
MS1	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,91	0,95	0,99	0,99		0,96	0,00	0,99
MS2	0,83	1,00	0,99	1,00	1,00	0,91	1,00	0,99	1,00	1,00	0,67		0,87	0,00	0,97
MS3		0,89	0,88	0,89	0,98		0,88	0,86	0,80	0,97		0,75	0,67	0,00	0,96
MS4	0,89	0,98	0,97	0,95	0,99	0,89	0,96	0,97	0,98	0,99	0,92	0,00	0,65	0,00	0,97

Table 7. F1-score results for surface roughness (Ra) in training, validation, and test

	F1-Score in Training							F1-Score in Validation							F1-Score in Test						
	13U	9U	6U	6O	9O	13O	NC	13U	9U	6U	6O	9O	13O	NC	13U	9U	6U	6O	9O	13O	NC
MS1	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,96	0,89	0,99	0,71	0,69			0,98		0,99
MS2	0,99	0,92	0,92				1,00	0,99	0,92	1,00				1,00	0,87	0,63	0,36				0,98
MS3		0,62	0,93	0,90	0,77	0,91	0,98		0,80	0,93	0,62	0,67	0,90	0,97		0,23	0,49	0,43	0,39	0,00	0,96
MS4	0,96	0,88	0,95	0,88			0,98	0,94	0,85	0,77	0,80			0,99	0,57	0,73	0,00	0,52			0,97

Table 8. F1-score results for diameter deviation (Ddev) in training, validation, and test

The first thing that can be deduced from Tables 7 and 8 is that the developed DL models can operate in a real scenario, as they are capable of effectively discriminating when the machine is machining and when it is not. The training and validation results are very high, exceeding 0.80 in all cases for the surface roughness variable (Ra). For diameter deviation (Ddev), there are greater doubts between classes, but in general, the metric results are high, not dropping below 0.62.

As for the prediction in the test, the performance for Ra remains at high levels for all MS except for MS3, where the results drop to values of 0.67 for class N8. For Ddev in the test, the performance decreases in all MS, being especially low for MS3. After analyzing this behavior of the models and comparing data between MS, it is concluded that both experiments should be repeated for MS3 to verify that the signals and quality parameters have been measured adequately, although there may be other reasons for these poor results. In cases where 0.00 appears in any class, this means that errors are generated by predicting values of that class when in reality that class is not present.

The inference of Ddev is considerably more complex than that of Ra. The DL model is multi-output, which implies that during training a compromise must be reached to simultaneously minimize the error in both variables. This compromise may cause adjustments aimed at improving the prediction of Ddev to penalize or negatively affect the result of Ra, making the joint optimization of both metrics difficult.

Although the confusion matrices are not included, this analysis is also interesting since errors occur between adjacent classes. Another phenomenon observed is that errors also occur in transition zones between NC and not NC. In the windowing process, this transition can occur in the middle of the window, leading to doubts about how to classify that sample.

4. - DISCUSSION

The four MS have carried out identical experiments to generate data aimed at developing models for intermediate and output quality prediction in machined parts, working with different machine configurations and varying the sensorization and number of available channels.

The main challenge identified lies in the fact that the machine characterization experiments do not cover all possible parameters (f_z , v_c , a_p) with which the machining of the parts in experiment 2 was later performed. This limitation generates a significant domain adaptation problem when these parameters exceed the maximum and minimum values learned during training. To mitigate this problem, it was necessary to incorporate the data from one of the five manufactured parts into the training set.

The complexity of DL modeling for the simultaneous prediction of Ra and Ddev has also been evidenced. While the prediction of Ra is feasible, the prediction of Ddev is considerably more difficult with the data supplied to the model (for example, it might require the incorporation of a temperature variable). This confirms the inherent complexity of multi-output models, where the optimization of one variable can compromise the performance of the other, highlighting the need for more balanced loss functions.

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Additionally, the number of experiments is insufficient to adequately train a complex multi-output DL model. The data augmentation strategy by windowing signals with overlap causes slight overfitting of the model, observable when comparing training and test metrics. Nevertheless, the model maintains satisfactory performance in the test trials.

This work highlights the critical importance of data quality. The MS3 center shows Ra measurement values in experiment 2 that are not consistent with those of its own experiment 1 nor with those of the rest of the manufacturing sites. The variability in performance between centers underlines the importance of the quality and representativeness of the training data, as well as the need to use output variable measurement sensors that are calibrated and with the same precision. This may also be due to the adaptive dynamic control that modern machining machines may have, which adapt machine parameters in real time. This can result in neither Ra nor Ddev falling within the classes foreseen in the experiment.

The manufacturing center that provides the best results is MS1, which is attributed to two main factors: on the one hand, it incorporates the largest number of information channels into the model and, on the other, it operates natively at 1 kHz, requiring less manipulation of the input signals. However, other centers with fewer input channels still provide good results.

Finally, the DL model architecture is transferable to the different manufacturing sites. The model adapts satisfactorily to the different number of input signals, with little work required to tune the network hyperparameters

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